

Participant	Role	Organization	Org. Size	Org. Domain	Software Type
P1, P2	Developer	O1	Medium	Productivity	SaaS, B2C
P3	Developer	O2	Small	Web Design	B2B
P4	Product Manager	O3	Medium	Communication	B2B
P5	Product Manager	O4	Medium	Finance	B2B
P6	Developer			Reservation Management	SaaS, B2B
P7	Customer Success				
P8	Developer				
P9	Product Manager	O6	Large	Health	Enterprise
P10, P11	Product Manager	O7	Large	Finance	SaaS, B2B
P12, P13	Developer				
P14	Developer	O8	Medium	Hospitality	SaaS, B2B
P15	Customer Success				
P16, P17	Developer				
P18	Developer	O10	Small	Communication	B2B
P19	Product Manager	O11	Medium	Finance	SaaS
P20	Quality Assurance				
P21	Developer	O12	Medium	Reservation Management	SaaS, B2B
P22	Customer Success				
P23	Developer				
P24	Quality Assurance	O13	Medium	Tourism	SaaS, B2B
P25	Product Manager	O14	Large	Search / Advertising	Enterprise
P26	Product Manager	O15	Medium	Communication	B2B
P27	Developer				
P28	Product Manager	O16	Medium	Finance	SaaS, B2B
P29	Developer				
P30	Developer				
P31	Product Manager	O18	Medium	Gaming	B2C
P32	Product Manager	O19	Large	Cloud Services	Enterprise
P33	Quality Assurance	O20	Medium	Gaming	B2C